

ACTIVITY OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION TEACHERS IN EDUCATING STUDENTS

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Abstract. This article describes the specific features of physical education activities of school physical education teacher in class and extracurricular activities.

Key words: lesson, physical education lesson, extracurricular activities, educational tasks, teacher's activities.

When analyzing the teacher's functional information, the content of his professional preparation related to the physical education of school teachers is revealed more fully. This responsibility imposes on him a special requirement of pedagogical activity. Some of them are defined by normative documents, so their implementation should be considered mandatory: the second part is beyond mandatory. They are connected with the teacher's social and physical education and educational activities with the help of sports equipment.

It is known that the organization of such educational work requires the use of all the reserves of the educational process in the higher educational institution, more grounded preparation for the formation of the future teacher-educator's motivational field.

According to R. Helman (1975), sports pedagogy should provide purposeful, understandable and planned study and development of a person through sports. H. Shvidman (1976) stated that the subject of sports pedagogy is sports activities (especially sports achievement activities). This is a difficult and exciting process for the purpose of comprehensive development of the athlete's personality. Sports pedagogy shows these features and expresses them theoretically. U. Neuman (1975) stated that sports pedagogy, like any other pedagogical sciences, is an objective process of differentiation, and has become a social phenomenon. L. Paul (1979) defines sports pedagogy based on his work, its place among sports sciences and the tasks set before it. The author proposes to determine the subject of sports pedagogy as a science based on the compatibility of the stages of development of sports pedagogy with the needs of society.

The entire pedagogical team of the school, the director, his deputy for educational affairs, the deputy for spiritual and educational affairs, the organizer of classroom and extracurricular activities, physical education teacher, head of

primary military training, class leaders, teachers, educators in extended day groups will participate. The development of students' physical abilities, the expansion of their functional capabilities, the growth of mental and physical work capacity, the strengthening of their health, and the upbringing of moral and will qualities depend on their knowledge, initiative and coordinated work.

Creating conditions for successful education of teachers, preparing them for life, work, conscious choice of profession, protection of the motherland.

Active inclusion of physical education in the educational process of the school allows students to form a healthy lifestyle and meaningful spending of free time. Recommendations on the system of educational work in secondary schools will help the teacher in this. These educations, which are aimed at the development of the student's personality and comprehensive education, contribute to the establishment of an effective action of the education system that affects the school, family and community together, and increase the leadership and organizational tasks of youth organizations such as New Generation and Kamalot. and activates students' self-management.

In the physical education of students, three main groups of tasks can be distinguished: health, educational and training, they are performed taking into account the anatomical, physiological and psychological characteristics of children.

The task of healing. It is aimed at the hormonal development of the body and preparing it for a gradually increasing load; ensuring the high stability of the body against the unpleasant effects of the external environment, physical fatigue, which ensures the development of physical abilities for students of this age. Performing fitness tasks either by students themselves (under the guidance of parents) by choosing special methods and tools that help normal physical development, or by combining educational and educational activities. possible

Educational duties. Pupils are directed to acquire knowledge, skills and abilities in the field of physical education for use in various conditions of life. This includes knowing about the effects and importance of physical exercises, taking into account the methods, rules and conditions of physical exercises.

Pupils' self-selected activities. Public activities outside of school (in residential areas, children's and teenagers' sports schools, student palaces, youth tourist stations, sports teams, neighborhoods, school and playgrounds, playgrounds, recreation independent physical activities in parks, etc.).

The effectiveness of the physical education system is primarily characterized by the involvement of all students in physical education, sports and tourism in

various forms of work outside the classroom and outside of school, their supervision, and the maximum introduction of physical exercises in the daily life of students.

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